

Horoyah: A Knowledge Graph-based Framework for Election Monitoring in Low and Middle-Income Countries

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Abstract. In many low and middle-income countries (LMICs), electoral processes are plagued by dysfunctions that undermine democratic principles and public trust. These issues, ranging from political corruption to a lack of transparency, often lead to post-election violence and contested results. Civil society organizations (CSOs) play a crucial role in mitigating these problems through election monitoring, but often lack the tools for effective, large-scale data collection and analysis. This paper introduces Horoyah, an innovative platform designed to empower civil society and the general public by leveraging knowledge graphs to promote transparency and accountability in election monitoring. Horoyah provides a structured framework for collecting, aggregating, and analysing citizen-reported election results from polling stations. Structuring voting data within a knowledge graph enables the platform to facilitate the identification of trends, inconsistencies, and potential irregularities, thereby enhancing data accuracy and providing an auditable record of the electoral process. We outline its design and demonstrate its application through a use case based on the 2020 presidential elections in Guinea, West Africa. We conclude by discussing the potential of such tools to fortify democratic practices while also considering the significant challenges of disinformation, cybersecurity, and the digital divide that they raise.

Keywords: Election Monitoring · Knowledge Graph · Civil Society · Transparency · LMIC · e-Democracy.

1 Introduction

The wave of democratization that swept across Africa in the early 1990s transitioned many nations from single-party rule to multi-party systems. Despite significant progress in the practice of holding elections, many have devolved into mere formalities that serve to approve political elites, undermining the credibility of the entire process. In many African Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs) like Guinea, Kenya, and Zimbabwe, electoral processes are frequently marred by claims of vote-rigging and subsequent violence. These dysfunctions permeate nearly every stage of the process, from the formation of politically compromised electoral bodies to the announcement of results, creating an environment ripe for irregularities. This systemic lack of transparency erodes voters' trust and makes the ideals of democracy unattainable.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been investigated as a means to implement e-democracy and combat corruption, with evidence suggesting that e-government systems can increase transparency [2]. Empirical studies have shown an inverse relationship between ICT usage and perceived corruption, highlighting technology's potential as a valuable tool in anti-corruption efforts [5].

In this context, Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) are critical actors in promoting electoral transparency [9]. Through independent observation and public awareness campaigns, CSOs contribute significantly to the credibility and integrity of elections [12]. The active engagement of citizens in monitoring elections is a cornerstone of a robust democracy, and technology offers a transformative potential to bolster this civic role [13].

This paper introduces Horoyah, a platform engineered to harness the power of knowledge graphs to advance election monitoring for civil society in LMICs. A knowledge graph is a structured data representation that organizes information and establishes connections between different data points [6]. Applying this to voting data allows for a more comprehensive analysis of the relationships between voter demographics, voting patterns, and results. This method enhances data accuracy, enables more efficient analysis, and promotes transparency by providing a clear, auditable trail. We present its overall design and implementation and a use case based on the 2020 Guinean presidential election. We argue that by providing tools for citizen-led data collection and analysis, Horoyah can empower CSOs and the public, fortifying democratic electoral practices in resource-constrained environments.

2 Background

The field of e-democracy has explored various technological interventions to improve electoral processes. Early studies focused on electronic polling services for creating polls and viewing results [2], while others advocated for e-democracy tools like "smart vote" to enhance democratic principles [8]. A significant body of research has been dedicated to internet voting, examining its advantages and challenges [12], and proposing secure, end-to-end verifiable systems like D-DEMOS [3]. In Estonia, a nationwide e-Election System has been implemented, allowing for online voting¹. These efforts highlight the long-standing interest in using ICT to improve the efficiency and transparency of elections.

Another stream of work focuses on making election data more accessible and usable. In the United States, for instance, the OpenElections project, launched in 2012, addresses the challenge of obtaining comprehensive and standardized election data². It utilizes a network of volunteers to collect and convert official results into standardized CSV formats, which are then shared on GitHub. This model has proven valuable for journalists and researchers. Similarly, the electiondata Python package was developed to help users consolidate, analyze, and visualize election results from various file formats [13].

In the context of LMICs, specific technological solutions have been proposed to address local challenges. In India for instance, an "Integrated Election Voting System" model was proposed to supplement existing Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs) with an e-voting channel to increase participation [9]. The study emphasized the potential for ICT to enhance India's electoral process and increase voter turnout. In Senegal, civil society initiatives like "Sénégal Ouvert" and open data repositories on GitHub demonstrate a growing movement towards election transparency through ICT technology³.

One innovative technological approach is the use of knowledge graphs for the collection and aggregation of voting data. The novelty of Horoyah includes the application of knowledge graphs

¹ <https://digiexpo.e-estonia.com/e-governance/e-democracy-and-open-data/e-election-system/>

² <https://github.com/openelections>

³ <https://github.com/senegalouvert>

to the voting domain. A knowledge graph offers a structured way to link diverse data points like voter demographics and voting patterns, enabling deeper analysis. This approach enhances data accuracy, facilitates efficient processing, and provides an auditable trail of data, which is crucial for transparency. Research has explored using networks-based approach to improve problems of poor service delivery and quality of care in low-income regions, aiming to foster more inclusive approaches [7]. Horoyah builds on these ideas to create a concrete, deployable platform specifically for civil society-led election monitoring in LMICs.

3 Overall description of the platform

3.1 Functional Components

The Horoyah platform is comprised of several key components that work together to create a seamless workflow for election monitoring.

Data Collection. Horoyah is designed for ease of use by citizen reporters at polling stations. A user-friendly, location-based smart form, similar to applications like Survey, is used for data entry. This allows observers to efficiently submit their observations, including vote counts and reports of any incidents.

Data Aggregation and Verification. Once submitted, the data is integrated into the Horoyah knowledge graph (please see Figure 1). A critical step in this process is verification. To maintain the integrity of the information, the W3C Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL)⁴ is used for validation, complemented by a team of volunteers screening each submission before it is taken into account within the knowledge graph and included on a public map or dashboard.

Analysis and Visualization. The true power of the knowledge graph lies in the analytical capabilities that it can enable. Linking voting data with demographic information and geographic locations enables the possibility to identify correlations and trends within the electorate, such as patterns based on age, gender, or socioeconomic status. Further, a crosscheck with the available national census and other demographic characteristics openly available could be possible. The platform can then visualize this enriched data through dashboards and interactive maps as shown in Figure 3, allowing the public and media to easily explore the results and focus on specific issues or areas.

Knowledge Graph Population. The verified data populates the ontology schema shown in Figure 1, creating a rich, interconnected dataset. This process automates and streamlines what would otherwise be a manual effort prone to errors and delays. The structured nature of the knowledge graph enhances data accuracy by minimizing inconsistencies during collection and aggregation.

⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

Cartographic Data. OpenStreetMap is used for the maps and geographical structures description⁵ [4] (but could also be LinkedGeoData⁶ [1]). The OpenStreetMap platform is built by a community of volunteer cartographers who contribute and maintain data on neighbourhoods, roads, trails, cafés, train stations and much more, all over the world. It is therefore an open, collaborative map of the world. It is improved every day by over a million contributors.

Fig. 1: The Horoyah Knowledge Graph model used in the platform

3.2 The Horoyah Knowledge Graph

The core component of Horoyah data and knowledge backbone is modelled as a knowledge graph, representing the various entities and their complex relationships within an electoral system. Figure 1 illustrates the ontology model of the knowledge graph. The core entities include the following notions.

⁵ <https://www.openstreetmap.org>

⁶ <https://linkedgeo.org/>

- **Administrative and Electoral Divisions:** The model captures the hierarchical structure of a country, from the national level down to RegionOrState, PrefectureOrDepartment, Municipality, and District.
- **Voting Infrastructure:** This includes VotingCenter and VotingStation, which are the primary locations where voting occurs and results are reported from. The model can be enhanced with geographical data from open sources like OpenStreetMap [4], which provides a collaborative map of the world built by volunteers. It could also be any other geographical data framework such as LinkedGeoData [1].
- **Electoral Process:** Key entities like ElectionType (e.g., PresidentialElection), PoliticalParty, and Candidate are central to the model. The VotingSession concept links these entities for a specific election event.
- **Actors and Results:** LocalAssessor represents the civil society observer or citizen who assesses the process and reports the Score (results) obtained by a Candidate at a VotingStation.

This interconnected structure allows the platform to link disparate pieces of information, such as results from a specific polling station, the political party of the candidates, and the demographic data of the electoral subdivisions.

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Fig. 2: Screenshot of the graph rendered with the OntoGraph panel of the Protégé editor tool.

3.3 Validating the Knowledge Graph

SHACL is a language for validating Resource Description Framework (RDF) based graphs against a set of conditions [11]. These conditions are provided as "shapes" and other constructs expressed in the form of an RDF graph. SHACL is a W3C Consortium recommendation that helps ensure data quality and consistency within a knowledge graph. Three examples are provided in the following listings, respectively for the CandidateShape, Subclass Shapes (ElectionTypeSubClassShape) and *participatesIn* property.

CandidateShape

```

1 @prefix oekg: <http://www.horoya.org/OpeneElectionKG#> .
2 @prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
3
4 oekg:CandidateShape
5   a sh:NodeShape ;
6   sh:targetClass oekg:Candidate ;
7   sh:property [
8     sh:path oekg:obtains ;
9     sh:class oekg:Score ;
10    sh:name "obtains" ;
11    sh:description "A candidate must obtain a score." ;
12    sh:minCount 1 ;
13  ] ;
14  sh:property [
15    sh:path oekg:represents ;
16    sh:class oekg:PoliticalParty ;
17    sh:name "represents" ;
18    sh:description "A candidate must represent a political party." ;
19    sh:minCount 1 ;
20  ] .

```

Subclass Shapes These shapes ensure that the ElectionType sub-classes axioms from the ontology are respected.

```

1 @prefix oekg: <http://www.horoya.org/OpeneElectionKG#> .
2 @prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
3 @prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
4
5 oekg:ElectionTypeSubClassShape
6   a sh:NodeShape ;
7   sh:targetClass oekg:LocalElection, oekg:PresidentialElection, oekg:
8   RepresentativeElection, oekg:SenateElection ;
9   sh:property [
10    sh:path rdf:type ;
11    sh:hasValue oekg:ElectionType .
12  ] .

```

Rules for *participatesIn* Property The *participatesIn* property links a *VotingStation* to a *VotingSession*. Here are some rules to validate this relationship : *sh* : *pathopenelectionKG* : *participatesIn*. This rule specifies the *participatesIn* property as the one to be validated. Here are some rules to validate this relationship.

- *sh:path* *openelectionKG:participatesIn*: This rule specifies the *participatesIn* property as the one to be validated.
- *sh:class* *openelectionKG:VotingStation*: This rule specifies that the subject of the *participatesIn* property must be an instance of the *VotingStation* class.
- *sh:targetClass* *openelectionKG:VotingSession*: This rule asserts that the object of the *participatesIn* property must be an instance of the *VotingSession* class.

```

1
2 @prefix sh: <http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
3 @prefix oekg: <http://www.horoya.org/OpeneElectionKG#> .
4
5 # Shape to validate the 'participatesIn' property of a VotingStation
6
7 oekg:VotingStationShape
8   a sh:NodeShape ;
9   sh:targetClass oekg:VotingStation ;
10
11   # Defines the property constraint
12   sh:property [
13     # This is the core of the rule, specifying the property to be validated
14     .
15     sh:path oekg:participatesIn ;
16
17     # Human-readable name for the rule
18     sh:name "Voting Station Participation" ;
19
20     # Description of what the rule checks
21     sh:description "Validates the participatesIn relationship for a
    VotingStation." ;
  ] .

```

3.4 Querying the Knowledge Graph

The Horoyah Knowledge graph is expressed in RDF using the triplet based representation. It can be queried therefore using the SPARQL query language. We provide in the following an example of a SPARQL query that calculates the total vote score for a given candidate from a specific political party in a given region of the country during a presidential election. The SELECT clause [... (SUM(?scoreValue) AS ?totalScoreInRegion)] selects the names of the candidate, party, and region, and most importantly, it calculates the sum (SUM) of all found score values (?scoreValue). It renames this total as ?totalScoreInRegion for clarity.

```

1
2   # Prefixes for readability
3 PREFIX oekg: <http://www.horoya.org/OpeneElectionKG#>
4 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
5 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
6
7 # Query to aggregate scores
8 SELECT ?candidateName ?partyName ?regionName (SUM(?scoreValue) AS ?
   totalScoreInRegion)
9 WHERE {
10   # 1. Identify the election type and the associated voting session
11   ?session rdf:type oekg:VotingSession .
12   # Assumption 1: The session is linked to an election type
13   ?session oekg:isForElectionType oekg:PresidentialElection .
14
15   # 2. Identify the candidate and the political party
16   ?candidate rdf:type oekg:Candidate .
17   ?candidate oekg:represents ?party .
18
19   # 3. Retrieve the candidate's score for this session
20   ?candidate oekg:obtains ?score .
21   # Assumption 2: The score is linked to a specific voting session
22   ?score oekg:inSession ?session .
23   # Assumption 3: The score has a numeric value
24   ?score oekg:hasValue ?scoreValue .
25
26   # 4. Link the vote to its geographical location (the Region)
27   ?station oekg:participatesIn ?session .
28   ?station oekg:belongsTo ?electoralDivision .
29   # Assumption 4: The electoral division is located in a region
30   ?electoralDivision oekg:locatedIn ?region .
31   ?region rdf:type oekg:RegionOrState .
32
33   # 5. Retrieve names for display (Assumption 5)
34   ?candidate rdfs:label ?candidateName .
35   ?party rdfs:label ?partyName .
36   ?region rdfs:label ?regionName .
37
38   # 6. Filter for the specified party and region
39   FILTER(?partyName = "GivenPartyName"@en)
40   FILTER(?regionName = "GivenRegionName"@en)
41 }
42 # 7. Group the results to sum by candidate/party/region
43 GROUP BY ?candidateName ?partyName ?regionName
44 # 8. Order the results
45 ORDER BY DESC(?totalScoreInRegion)

```

4 Illustration: the Guinea’s 2020 presidential elections

4.1 Context of the presidential elections

Guinea is a republic located in the West African region and a member of the ECOWAS regional organization. A Presidential elections were held on 18 October 2020, with incumbent president Alpha Condé (RPG party) running for a third term against former prime minister Cellou Dalein Diallo (UFDG party) and various other candidates. Earlier in that year, a controversial constitutional referendum reset presidential term limits, allowing Condé to run again. Despite opposition boycotts and protests against Condé’s government, the elections went ahead alongside a legislative vote. The electoral process, overseen by the independent electoral commission (CENI), used a two-round system where the President is elected by an absolute majority vote for a 5-year term. The country’s population during the 2020 election was reported as 12,527,440, with an estimated 5,179,600 registered voters in 2020 ⁷. Initial reports indicated that Diallo was in the lead, and on 19 October, he declared victory prematurely based on his party’s polling, which was criticized by Condé. However, with 96.14% of votes counted, the national election committee (CENI) officially announced Condé as the winner in the first round with 59.49% of the vote on 24 October. During the voting date and the following days, the Union of Free Radios and Televisions of Guinea (URTELGUI), an independent SCO monitored around 11% of the voting stations nationally, which involved 250 journalists. A dedicated radio broadcast was used to report the results. We used the available dataset to instantiate Horoyah. Table 1 summarizes the official results as provided by the CENI. These results were strongly contested by the 2nd place candidate and his party. As could be seen, SCO based results, as depicted in Figure 3 suggest a noticeable difference with those provided by the official CENI committee. This raises the issue of the transparency during the official aggregation and counting process of the election results.

Table 1: Results of the 2020 presidential elections as proclaimed by the CENI

Candidate	Political Part	Votes obtained	Percentage
Alpha Condé	RPG	2,438,815	59.49
Cellou Dalein Diallo	UFDG	1,373,320	33.50
Ibrahima Abé Sylla	NGR	63,676	1.55
Ousmane Kaba	PADES	48,623	1.19

5 Discussions

The integration of digital tools like Horoyah into election monitoring presents both profound opportunities and significant challenges. While they can enhance transparency and empower citizens and CSO, they also introduce vulnerabilities that must be carefully managed to safeguard electoral integrity.

⁷ <https://www.idea.int/data-tools/country-view/115/40>

Fig. 3: Observed results nationwide by the URTELGUI SCO, with an highlight for Kankan, a north-east region in Guinea. The yellow colour if for the candidate of the RPG party while the green colour for the UFDG.

5.1 Benefits and Opportunities

The primary benefit of a framework like Horoyah is the enhancement of transparency and public trust. By providing a transparent avenue for reporting and addressing issues, the system promotes accountability. Online platforms also improve accessibility, allowing voters to participate in the democratic process from various locations, which can lead to increased voter participation, especially among younger, tech-savvy demographics. Furthermore, transitioning from paper-based reporting to digital systems contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing paper waste and the carbon footprint associated with elections.

5.2 Challenges and Limitations

Despite the benefits, the deployment of such technologies is fraught with challenges. We highlight in the following sections some of them.

Disinformation and Cybersecurity A major concern is the risk of disinformation. Malicious actors could attempt to undermine the system by flooding it with false reports. This necessitates robust verification mechanisms and collaboration between civil society and media to counteract misleading information. Cybersecurity is another pressing issue. Online systems are vulnerable to cyber threats, including denial-of-service (DoS) attacks that could disrupt the reporting process, and hacking that could compromise the privacy and anonymity of reporters.

The Digital Divide In many LMICs, limited internet access and varying levels of digital literacy pose significant barriers to participation. A digital-only platform risks excluding large segments of the population, particularly in rural areas. Any successful implementation must consider context-sensitive approaches, potentially integrating with lower-tech solutions like SMS or providing offline capabilities.

Platform Integrity Digital platforms like WhatsApp and Telegram have been used in countries like Brazil and India to disseminate misinformation and coordinate attacks on the electoral process. This highlights that the platforms themselves can become vectors for undermining electoral integrity, often lacking robust policies to operate safely in diverse linguistic and cultural contexts ⁸.

5.3 The Role of AI and Future Trends

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents a new frontier of challenges and opportunities for elections. Generative AI can be used to create highly realistic "deepfakes" and spread disinformation on an unprecedented scale, posing a critical risk to election integrity ⁹. Lawmakers and civil society must prepare to address these evolving threats.

However, AI also offers powerful tools that can be harnessed for good. AI algorithms could be integrated into Horoyah to perform advanced analysis on incoming data, automatically detecting anomalies and flagging potential irregularities for review. As envisioned in the project's future work, AI could also power voice-based applications for low-literacy users [10], making the reporting process more inclusive. The key will be to develop these technologies responsibly, with a focus on augmenting human oversight rather than replacing it, to ensure they strengthen rather than subvert democratic processes.

6 Conclusion and Perspectives

This paper has introduced Horoyah, an ongoing work on a knowledge graph-based framework designed to empower civil society and citizens in monitoring elections within the challenging environments of LMICs. The knowledge graph is available online on Zenodo¹⁰. We have argued that dysfunctions in electoral processes erode public trust and that ICT, when applied thoughtfully, can be a powerful tool for transparency and accountability. By providing a structured, auditable, and accessible platform for citizen-reported data, Horoyah enables CSOs and the public to play a more effective role in safeguarding democratic integrity.

The use case of the 2020 Guinea election illustrates the platform's potential to provide an independent, evidence-based counter-narrative to official results, thereby fostering public confidence and holding institutions accountable. However, we recognize that the path to effective implementation is filled with challenges, including the pervasive threats of disinformation, cybersecurity risks, and the digital divide. Overcoming these obstacles requires a collaborative, context-sensitive approach involving CSOs, technologists, media organizations, and electoral bodies.

⁸ <https://www.techpolicy.press/security-and-reliability-concerns-around-internet-voting-outweigh-benefits/>

⁹ <https://www.brennancenter.org/our-work/analysis-opinion/election-year-risks-ai>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16879062>

As we look to the future, the rise of AI presents both new threats and new opportunities. The goal must be to steer the development of these powerful technologies towards strengthening democratic institutions. Frameworks like Horoyah represent a crucial step in this direction—harnessing the power of data and technology not to replace human judgment, but to empower citizen engagement and build a more transparent and trustworthy democratic future. That is why for low-literacy users, the future work of the Horoyah project envisions using AI-powered voice-based applications to make the reporting process more inclusive and invest in educating end-users to deal with the platform.

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References

1. Baader, F., Knechtel, M., Peñaloza, R.: A Generic Approach for Large-Scale Ontological Reasoning in the Presence of Access Restrictions to the Ontology’s Axioms. In: Hutchison, D., Kanade, T., Kittler, J., Kleinberg, J.M., Mattern, F., Mitchell, J.C., Naor, M., Nierstrasz, O., Pandu Rangan, C., Steffen, B., Sudan, M., Terzopoulos, D., Tygar, D., Vardi, M.Y., Weikum, G., Bernstein, A., Karger, D.R., Heath, T., Feigenbaum, L., Maynard, D., Motta, E., Thirunarayan, K. (eds.) *The Semantic Web - ISWC 2009*, vol. 5823, pp. 49–64. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2009). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-04930-9_4
2. Bouras, C., Katris, N., Triantafyllou, V.: An Electronic Polling Service to Support Public Awareness Using Web Technologies. *ECIS 2001 Proceedings (Jan 2001)*, <https://aisel.aisnet.org/ecis2001/14>
3. Chondros, N., Zhang, B., Zacharias, T., Diamantopoulos, P., Maneas, S., Patsonakis, C., Delis, A., Kiayias, A., Roussopoulos, M.: D-DEMOS: A Distributed, End-to-End Verifiable, Internet Voting System. In: *2016 IEEE 36th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)*. pp. 711–720. IEEE, Nara, Japan (Jun 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCS.2016.56>, <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7536569/>
4. contributors, O.: Planet dump retrieved from <https://planet.osm.org> (2017), <https://www.openstreetmap.org>
5. Erdely, A.: A copula based approach for electoral quick counts (2019). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17665.71526>, <http://rgdoi.net/10.13140/RG.2.2.17665.71526>
6. Hogan, A., Blomqvist, E., Cochez, M., D’amato, C., Melo, G.D., Gutierrez, C., Kirrane, S., Gayo, J.E.L., Navigli, R., Neumaier, S., Ngomo, A.C.N., Polleres, A., Rashid, S.M., Rula, A., Schmelzeisen, L., Sequeda, J., Staab, S., Zimmermann, A.: Knowledge Graphs. *ACM Computing Surveys* **54**(4), 1–37 (May 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447772>, <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3447772>
7. Kalaris, K., Wong, G., English, M.: Understanding networks in low-and middle-income countries’ health systems: A scoping review. *PLOS Global Public Health* **3**(1), e0001387 (Jan 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0001387>, <https://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0001387>
8. Ladner, A., Pianzola, J.: Do Voting Advice Applications Have an Effect on Electoral Participation and Voter Turnout? Evidence from the 2007 Swiss Federal Elections. In: Tambouris, E., Macintosh, A., Glassey, O. (eds.) *Electronic Participation*, vol. 6229, pp. 211–224. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2010). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-15158-3_18

9. Matharu, G.S., Mishra, A., Chaudhary, L.: Integrated Election Voting System: A Model for Leveraging ICT in the Indian Election Scenario. In: Proceedings of the 2014 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology for Competitive Strategies. pp. 1–7. ACM, Udaipur Rajasthan India (Oct 2014). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2677855.2677944>, <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2677855.2677944>
10. Ouedraogo, I., Some, B.M.J., Oyibo, K., Benedikter, R., Diallo, G.: Evaluating a phone-based Interactive Voice Response system for reducing misinformation and improving malaria literacy. *Information Technology for Development* pp. 1–27 (Nov 2024). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2024.2414193>, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/02681102.2024.2414193>
11. Rabbani, K., Lissandrini, M., Hose, K.: SHACL and ShEx in the Wild: A Community Survey on Validating Shapes Generation and Adoption. In: Companion Proceedings of the Web Conference 2022. pp. 260–263. ACM, Virtual Event, Lyon France (Apr 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3487553.3524253>, <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3487553.3524253>
12. Schryen, G.: E-Democracy: Internet Voting. Universität Regensburg (2003). <https://doi.org/10.5283/EPUB.21239>, <https://epub.uni-regensburg.de/id/eprint/21239>
13. Singer, S., Tsai, E.: electiondata: a Python package for consolidating, checking, analyzing, visualizing and exporting election results. *Journal of Open Source Software* **7**(69), 3739 (Jan 2022). <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03739>, <https://joss.theoj.org/papers/10.21105/joss.03739>